

NON-STATE FORMS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT IN UKRAINE

Orlov Viktor Anatoliiovych

*associate Professor of the Department of General Legal Disciplines
Donetsk Law Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine,
Ph.D. in Legal Sciences*

Part 2 of Article 3 of the Basic Law of Ukraine states that «the establishment and protection of human rights and freedoms is the main duty of the state». In turn, the constitutional principle of the rule of law provides for the establishment of the rule of law, which must guarantee everyone the establishment and protection of human rights and freedoms [1].

In Ukraine, law enforcement has always been associated with the activities of state bodies, but these bodies today, under various circumstances, are not able to fully ensure the security of all systems operating in society. The European vector of Ukraine's development, the processes of decentralization and deconcentration of power, and the urgent need to create a safe environment have led to the development of non-state forms of law enforcement.

The theoretical basis for the study are the scientific works of famous Ukrainian legal scholars: V. Bonyak [2], O. Vakarova [3], M. Zavalny [4], T. Podorozhna [5], O. Solonenko [6], S Yurka [7] and others.

The purpose of scientific research is a comprehensive study of theoretical and legal problems of the constitutional and legal content of non-state forms of law enforcement in Ukraine. Achieving the objective is ensured by the implementation of the following tasks: constitutional and legal definition and analysis of the state of legal regulation of non-state forms of law and order; identification of unresolved issues and suggestions on ways to solve them in this area.

When researching non-state forms of law enforcement, it is first necessary to clarify the meaning of the terms «law and order» and «law enforcement».

T. Podorozhna in her dissertation offers the following definition: «Law and order is a qualitative factual state of regulation of social relations, based on the implementation of law and provided with a special constitutional and legal mechanism» [5, p. 85]. We can fully agree with the given definition of law and order in the context of our study.

Most scholars who study the concepts of law enforcement and law enforcement agencies emphasize the exclusively state component of this activity.

«Law enforcement agencies» are referred to in Part 3 of Article 17 of the Constitution of Ukraine: «Ensuring state security and protection of the state border of Ukraine are entrusted to the relevant military formations and law enforcement agencies of the state, the organization and procedure of which are determined by law». And about «law enforcement agencies» it is specified in point 2 of part 1 of article 131-1 of the Basic law of Ukraine: «In Ukraine the prosecutor's office which carries out: /... / 2) the organization and procedural management of pre-judicial investigation proceedings, supervision of covert and other investigative and investigative actions of law enforcement agencies».

In turn, part 1 of Article 19 of the Constitution of Ukraine states: «The legal order in Ukraine is based on the principles according to which no one can be forced to do what is not provided by law». There are no other mentions of law enforcement.

Undoubtedly, the lack of a constitutional definition of law enforcement agencies has a negative impact on their effectiveness, on the establishment of law and order in all spheres of public life.

As V. Bonyak rightly notes, in the constitutional consolidation of the foundations of the legal status of law enforcement agencies there is an additional guarantee of the constitutional order, proper protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens [2, p. 45].

Therefore, the position of those researchers who consider it necessary during the formation of the strategy of law and order to change the tasks and activities of law enforcement agencies, transforming them from state institutions to social [8, p. 9].

In other words, the format of the modern definition of the problem requires the search for opportunities for the development of security engineering with the involvement of non-governmental elements of law enforcement.

In the process of dealing with the relevant issues, it is necessary to pay attention to the international legal practice, in which the term «Law Enforcement Agencies» is used to refer to law enforcement officials who constantly perform their duties. Those officials serve the community and protect all people from wrongdoing in accordance with the high degree of responsibility required in their profession.

UN General Assembly Resolution 34/169 «Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials» of 17 December 1979 states: «(c) Every law enforcement official is part of the criminal justice system aimed at preventing crime and that the behavior of each official of this system affects the whole system»[9].

Based on this definition, we can say that a law enforcement official is not only an official of a state body, he may also have a non-governmental form of activity.

Recognition by the state of non-state forms of law enforcement will only have a positive effect or affect its maintenance. O. Vakarova rightly notes in this regard in his dissertation research: «We need to make the law enforcement system as transparent and friendly as possible for society. It is important in this area to conduct a thorough decentralization and implementation of effective mechanisms of public control over law enforcement agencies» [3, p. 196].

Given that the function of law enforcement, in our opinion, is implemented in two forms: state and non-state - respectively, «form of law enforcement» (my italics. - VA), we propose to understand as an external manifestation of specific actions carried out by state and non-state elements of the law enforcement system in order to protect human rights and freedoms, law enforcement.

The functioning of the institution of non-state labor protection is actively studied by both domestic and foreign scientists. In his scientific work, S. Yurko substantiated the opinion that the main law enforcement functions and the main features of law enforcement activities may belong to non-state entities, which gives grounds for using the term «non-state law enforcement activities».

The scientist is convinced that non-state law enforcement activity should be understood as a specialized activity of civil society institutions to search for persons hiding from justice, disclosure of offenses, protection of individuals and legal entities, their property and public order from unlawful encroachments by law. He also stressed that non-state law enforcement is a separate type of law enforcement [7, p. 70].

Scholar-lawyer M. Zavalny defined the concept of non-state law enforcement activity as «regulated by the norms of administrative law type of activity, which consists in providing citizens and organizations with services that have a contractual, paid or free public nature, carried out to protect and safeguard legal rights and interests of citizens, organizations, society and the state in the manner and forms prescribed by law» [4, p. 10].

Serhiy Yurko, already mentioned, in his research includes the main subjects of non-state law enforcement: 1) private security companies; 2) enterprise security services; 3) private detective associations, or detectives who carry out their activities individually; 4) public formations for the protection of public order and the state border; 5) public assistants to law enforcement officers and other individual legal forms of assistance to law enforcement agencies [7, p. 94–95].

Some authors add lawyers, private notaries, private executors, and other human rights actors to the list.

Article 7 of the Constitution of Ukraine states that local self-government is recognized and guaranteed in Ukraine, so it is no coincidence that one of the functions of local self-government, according to current legislation (in particular, Article 38 of the Law of Ukraine «On Local Self-Government in Ukraine», is, protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens.

These issues (protection of law and order) are extremely important for local self-government - a specific form of public authority of the territorial community [6, p. 4–5].

In view of the above, it is clear that when other researchers identified the subjects of non-state law enforcement, it was not taken into account that non-state law enforcement activities can also be not only private but also public. Therefore, it is fair to add to this classification the activities of municipal law enforcement agencies, which with the beginning of the decentralization reform play a significant role in law enforcement activities on the ground. Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to distinguish between private, municipal and public forms of law enforcement.

Private forms of law enforcement include:

- 1) private security companies;
- 2) private detective associations, or detectives who carry out their activities individually.

To the municipal forms of law enforcement we include the following activities:

- 1) municipal guard;
- 2) municipal parking inspectors;
- 3) municipal employees performing law enforcement functions:
 - specialists in interaction with law enforcement agencies and ensuring public order, landscaping;
 - law enforcement and landscaping inspectors;
 - instructors to inform the public about the prevention of public order violations.

The public forms of law enforcement include the following activities:

- 1) public formations for the protection of public order;
- 2) security coordination offices;

3) public assistants of a district police officer on a voluntary basis.

Each of these elements, despite the lack of legal regulation of their activities, plays an important role in ensuring law and order in Ukraine.

In the absence of legal support for the activities of non-state law enforcement agencies, they are legalized by symbiosis with institutions whose legal status has already been determined. The activities of private detectives are ensured by a combination of the status of private security guard and lawyer. A clear example of symbiosis is the activity of the municipal guard, where local councils went through a combination of two forms of municipal security - self-governing bodies and voluntary institutions - in order to empower local government officials to wear special means of defense [10] and apply physical measures.

For example, employees of KP «Municipal Guard» (with a license to conduct security activities) are also members of the public formation for the protection of public order (Kyiv, Bar, Vinnytsia region) [11].

Scientific investigations and the author's own experience oblige to take into account that the constitutional and legal processing of the rule of law with the involvement of non-state forms of its protection is an important form of security engineering and an effective institution for human and civil rights and freedoms in Ukraine. The existing experience of functioning of non-state - private, municipal and public - forms of law enforcement, which is based on the provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine, demonstrates its effectiveness.

References

1. Rishennia Konstytutsiinoho Sudu Ukrainy u spravi za konstytutsiinym zvernenniam hromadianyna Bahinskoho Artema Oleksandrovycha shchodo ofitsiinoho tlumachennia polozhen chastyny pershoi statti 14-1 Kodeksu Ukrainy pro administratyvni pravoporushennia (sprava pro administratyvnu vidpovidalnist u sferi zabezpechennia bezpeky dorozhnoho rukhu) vid 22 hrudnia 2010 roku № 23-rp/2010 [Decision of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine in the case on the constitutional appeal of the citizen Bahinsky Artem Oleksandrovych regarding the official interpretation of the provisions of part one of Article 14-1 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses]. URL: <http://www.ccu.gov.ua/sites/default/files/ndf/23-rp/2010.doc> (data zvernennia: 01.02.2021) [in Ukrainian].
2. Boniak, V. O. (2016). Konstytutsiino-pravovi zasady orhanizatsii ta funktsionuvannia orhaniv okhorony pravoporiadku Ukrainy: problemy teorii i praktyky [Constitutional and legal principles of organization and functioning of law enforcement agencies of Ukraine: problems of theory and practice]: dys. ... d-ra yuryd. nauk: 12.00.02. Kharkiv. 500 s. [in Ukrainian].

3. Vakarova, O. V. (2019). Konstytutsiino-pravovyi status pravookhoronnykh orhaniv: suchasni pidkhody [Constitutional and legal status of law enforcement agencies: modern approaches] : dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk : 12.00.02. Uzhhorod. 260 s. [in Ukrainian].
4. Zavalnyi, M. V. (2018). Administratyvno-pravovi zasady diialnosti ta vzaiemodii derzhavnykh ta nederzhavnykh subiektiv pravookhorony v Ukraini [Administrative and legal principles of activity and interaction of state and non-state law enforcement entities in Ukraine] : avtoref. dys. ... d-ra yuryd. nauk. Kharkiv. 33 s. [in Ukrainian].
5. Podorozhna, T. S. (2017). Pravovyi poriadok: teoretyko-metodolohichni zasady konstytutsionalizatsii [Legal order: theoretical and methodological principles of constitutionalization] : dys. ... d-ra yuryd. nauk : 12.00.01; 12.00.02. Kyiv. 503 s. [in Ukrainian].
6. Solonenko, O. M. (2001). Realizatsiia funktsii zabezpechennia zakonnosti, pravoporiadku, okhorony prav, svobod i zakonnykh interesiv hromadian u systemi mistsevoho samovriaduvannia (orhanizatsiino-pravovi pytannia) [Implementation of the function of ensuring law and order, protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens in the system of local self-government (organizational and legal issues)] : avtoref. dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk : 12.00.02. Kyiv. 16 s. [in Ukrainian].
7. Iurko, S. S. (2017). Nederzhavna okhoronna i pravookhoronna diialnist [Non-governmental security and law enforcement activities] : dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk : 12.00.10. Odesa. 201 s. [in Ukrainian].
8. Pashulia, H. Ya. (2019). Orhany vnutrishnykh sprav yak element aparatu derzhavy v umovakh hlobalizatsii [Law enforcement agencies as an element of the state apparatus in the context of globalization]: avtoref. dys. ... kand. yuryd. nauk. Lviv. 19 s. [in Ukrainian].
9. Rezoliutsiia 34/169 Heneralnoi Asamblei OON «Kodeks povedinky posadovykh osib z pidtrymannia pravoporiadku» [«Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials»]. URL: http://zakon3.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_282 (data zvernennia: 05.12.2021) [in Russian].
10. Chleny Munokhorony ozbroiysia travmatychnymy pistoletamy [Members of the Municipal security armed themselves with traumatic pistols]. URL: <https://hmarochos.kiev.ua/2021/01/28/chleny-munohorony-ozbroyilysya-travmatychnymy-pistoletamy/> (data zvernennia: 01.02.2021) [in Ukrainian].
11. Tarasova, M., Vyshnytska, A. (2018) Ne tilky politsiia [Not only the police]. *Dzerkalo tyzhnia*. Vypusk № 34. URL: https://dt.ua/article/print/SOCIUM/ne-tilki-policiya-288446_.html (data zvernennia: 03.01.2021) [in Ukrainian].